

1 **A theoretical optimal experiment for accurate parameter estimation of a**
2 **dynamic rumen model representing the *Asparagopsis taxiformis* effect on *in***
3 ***vitro* methane production**

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13 **Abstract**

14 Reducing methane (CH₄) emissions from ruminants is a major target for the livestock
15 sector. Synergy between *in vitro* studies and mathematical models can be useful to
16 provide high quality data enabling to quantify the mode of action of anti-
17 methanogenic additives and thus design robust mitigation solutions. The objective of
18 this work was to conduct a theoretical optimal experiment design (OED) to
19 determining optimal experimental conditions allowing an accurate estimation of key
20 parameters of a model we previously developed representing the impact of the anti-
21 methanogenic macroalgae *Asparagopsis taxiformis* on rumen fermentation and CH₄
22 under *in vitro* continuous conditions. *A. taxiformis* contains the anti-methanogenic
23 compound bromoform which inhibits directly the growth rate of methanogens. CH₄
24 inhibition results in hydrogen (H₂) accumulation. H₂ exerts thermodynamic control on

25 the fermentation *via* the flux allocation towards volatile fatty acids production. We
26 applied the OED framework to 5 model parameters related to the mode of action of
27 *A. taxiformis*: k_1 (inhibitor bromoform constant) and p_1, p_2, p_3, p_4 (parameters of affine
28 functions representing flux allocation factors). After conducting a structural parameter
29 identifiability analysis to guarantee that the parameter identification problem was
30 well-posed, we set the OED problem for parameter estimation using the D-optimality
31 criterion which maximizes the determinant of the Fisher information matrix (FIM)
32 using as decision variables the bromoform content in the feed and five sampling
33 times for a run duration of 24 h. The OED problem was solved for four feed intake
34 patterns. The accuracy of the parameter estimates was determined by the calculation
35 of the standard deviations (s.d.) and compared with the s.d. obtained with a classical
36 equidistant sampling protocol. The resulting optimal solutions were shown to be
37 specific to each feed distribution pattern. The gain in accuracy of the OED protocol
38 with respect to the equidistant sampling depended on the pattern of feed intake. For
39 the highest gain, the s.d. by the OED protocol were in average 57% of the s.d. of the
40 equidistant sampling protocol. For the lowest gain, the s.d. of the OED protocol were
41 in average 92% of the s.d. of the equidistant sampling protocol. These results
42 demonstrate the potential of the OED approach for obtaining accurate parameter
43 estimates, and highlight the importance of selecting an optimal supply of feed
44 additives. Using the OED approach can be instrumental for conducting experiments
45 that produce data for building robust rumen fermentation dynamic models that can
46 help the design of CH₄ mitigation strategies.

47

48 **Keywords:** optimal experiment design, parameter identification, macroalgae,
49 methane inhibition, rumen model

50

51 **Implications**

52 The use of antimethanogenic feed additives (AMFA) is a potent strategy to reduce
53 methane emissions from ruminants. Mathematical models can be instrumental for
54 designing optimal strategies of AMFA supply. To achieve this goal, models must be
55 robust. Here, we used the optimal experiment design framework in a dynamic
56 mathematical model representing the impact of the antimethanogenic macroalgae *A.*
57 *taxiformis* on *in vitro* rumen fermentation and methane production. We identified
58 theoretical experimental conditions with high informative content for accurately
59 estimating key model parameters. This approach has a great potential for the
60 development of robust models that could be useful for designing methane mitigation
61 strategies.

62 **Introduction**

63 Reducing methane (CH₄) emissions from ruminants is a major target for the livestock
64 sector. Agricultural CH₄ emissions must be decreased by 11 to 30% of the 2010 level
65 by 2030 and by 24 to 47% by 2050 to meet the 1.5°C target of the Paris Agreement
66 (IPCC, 2022). CH₄ mitigation can be achieved by the supply of antimethanogenic
67 feed additives (AMFA) (Arndt et al., 2022). Mechanistic modelling can be
68 instrumental to relate AMFA efficacy to fundamental elements of the rumen
69 fermentative system and for optimizing AMFA supply (Pressman & Kebreab, 2024;
70 Dijkstra et al., 2025).. To date, only two mechanistic models represent the effect of
71 AMFA on rumen fermentation and methane. The model of van Lingen et al. (2021)
72 represents the effect of 3-nitroxypropanol (3NOP) under *in vivo* conditions. The

73 model of Muñoz-Tamayo et al. (2021) represents the effect of bromoform from the
74 macroalgae *Asparagopsis taxiformis* under *in vitro* conditions. In this work, we focus
75 on *A. taxiformis* as AMFA. This red macroalgae contains the anti-methanogenic
76 compound bromoform (Machado et al., 2016a). The effect of *A. taxiformis* is dose
77 dependent with methane reductions from 75 to 99% *in vitro* (Huang et al., 2023;
78 (Machado et al., 2016b) and from 33 to 98% *in vivo* (Romero et al., 2024; Roque et
79 al., 2021; Kinley et al., 2020). As discussed by Belanche et al. (2025), the
80 elucidation of the mode of action of AMFA requires a multidisciplinary approach
81 covering microbiology and animal metabolism and dedicated experiments both *in*
82 *vitro* and *in vivo*. The synergy between experimentation and mathematical models
83 offers a great opportunity for the design of informative experiments with high quality
84 data enabling to quantify the AMFA mode of action and provide robust models with
85 capabilities for the design of mitigation strategies. However, such a synergy is rarely
86 exploited since model construction and parameter estimation is often conducted as
87 downstream process (after data collection). On the contrary, an upstream approach
88 could be adopted to identify optimal experimental conditions that guarantee the
89 identifiability of parameters and produce experimental data allowing accurate
90 estimation of model parameters (Muñoz-Tamayo and Tedeschi, 2023) and
91 characterisation of key mechanisms. By applying a dynamic sensitivity analysis using
92 the Shapley effects, Blondiaux et al. (2025) showed the importance of considering
93 the dynamics for an accurate quantification of the mechanisms driving rumen
94 fermentation and CH₄ production under methane inhibited conditions. The work
95 identified as perspective the application of the OED framework to identify optimal
96 sampling times and experimental conditions to provide data with high informative
97 content for accurately estimating model parameters. Accurate parameter estimates

98 are central for the construction of robust models with high predictability capabilities.
99 Accordingly, the objective of this work was to conduct a theoretical OED providing
100 information on optimal sampling times and AMFA doses for attaining accurate
101 estimates of key parameters of a model representing the impact of the *A. taxiformis*
102 on rumen fermentation and CH₄ under continuous *in vitro* conditions. Following Open
103 Science practices to promote accessibility and reproducibility (Muñoz-Tamayo et al.,
104 2022), the mathematical developments and the scripts that support this work are
105 freely available at Muñoz-Tamayo (2026) and in the link:
106 https://github.com/rafaelmunoztamayo/OED_rumen.

107 **Material and methods**

108 ***Mathematical model***

109 We used the mathematical model developed by Blondiaux et al., (2025) that
110 represents rumen microbial fermentation under methane inhibition conditions
111 provided by the supply of the *A. taxiformis*. The model represents *in vitro* continuous
112 conditions similar to a RUSITEC system. The operational conditions were taken from
113 the setting used in Belanche et al. (2017) with the volume of the liquid phase $V_1= 0.74$
114 L. The dynamics of the dry matter intake DMI (g/h) was represented by the following
115 equation:

$$116 \quad DMI(t) = \sum_{j=1}^{n_r} \frac{\omega_j \cdot DM_{total}}{n_r} \cdot e^{-k \cdot t} \quad (1)$$

117 With DM_{total} the daily total dry matter ingested, set to 11.25 g. The parameter k is
118 the intake kinetic rate constant, set to 0.015 h⁻¹. The parameter n_r is the number of
119 feed distributions per day, ω_j is the fraction of the total DM supplied in the distribution
120 j . We studied four conditions of feed distribution to explore different feeding patterns:

- 121 1) $n_r = 1$.
- 122 2) $n_r = 2$ with equal DM supply across the feed distributions ($\omega_j = 0.5$).
- 123 3) $n_r = 2$ with the first feed distribution accounting for 70% of the total DM ($\omega_1 =$
- 124 $0.7; \omega_2 = 0.3$).
- 125 4) $n_r = 4$ with equal DM supply across the feed distributions ($\omega_j = 0.25$).

126 Figure 1 shows an example of the *DMI* pattern with two distributions ($n_r = 2$) and

127 $\omega_1 = 0.7, \omega_2 = 0.3$.

128 The model extended the model previously developed by Muñoz-Tamayo et al. (2021)

129 under *in vitro* batch conditions, whose parameters were estimated using *in vitro*

130 experimental data from Chagas et al. (2019). The model is derived from mass

131 balance equations, following the structure of the rumen fermentation model

132 developed by Muñoz-Tamayo et al. (2016). Figure 2 displays the flow transport of the

133 system. Figure 3 shows the macroscopic representation of the rumen fermentation

134 process and the impact of *A. taxiformis* on the methanogenesis and on the

135 fermentation.

136 The mathematical model is described in compact way as

$$137 \frac{d\xi}{dt} = \mathbf{S} \cdot \boldsymbol{\rho}(\xi, \mathbf{p}) - \mathbf{g}(\xi, \mathbf{p}) \quad (2)$$

138 Where ξ is the vector of 19 state variables (compartments in Fig. 3), defined by $\xi =$

139 $(\mathbf{z}, \mathbf{s}, \mathbf{x}, \mathbf{s}_g)$, where $\mathbf{z} = (z_{\text{ndf}}, z_{\text{nsc}}, z_{\text{pro}})$ is the vector of concentrations of the polymer

140 components (neutral detergent fiber (z_{ndf}), non-structural carbohydrates (z_{nsc}) and

141 proteins (z_{pro}); g/L), $\mathbf{s} = (s_{\text{su}}, s_{\text{aa}}, s_{\text{ac}}, s_{\text{bu}}, s_{\text{pr}}, s_{\text{IN}}, s_{\text{IC}}, s_{\text{H}_2}, s_{\text{CH}_4}, s_{\text{br}})$ is the vector of

142 concentrations of the soluble components (sugars (s_{su}), amino acids (s_{aa}), acetate

143 (s_{ac}), butyrate (s_{bu}), propionate (s_{pr}), inorganic nitrogen (s_{IN}), inorganic carbon (s_{IC}),

144 hydrogen (s_{H_2}), CH_4 (s_{CH_4}); mol/L and bromoform (s_{br}); g/L), $\mathbf{x} = (x_{\text{su}}, x_{\text{aa}}, x_{\text{H}_2})$ is the

145 vector of concentrations of the microbial functional groups (sugars utilizers (x_{su}),
146 amino acids utilizers (x_{aa}) and hydrogen utilizers (x_{H_2}); mol/L), $\mathbf{s}_g =$
147 ($s_{g,CO_2}, s_{g,H_2}, s_{g,CH_4}$) is the vector of concentrations in gas phase (carbon dioxide
148 (s_{g,CO_2}), hydrogen (s_{g,H_2}) and CH_4 (s_{g,CH_4}); mol/L). $\boldsymbol{\rho}(\cdot)$ is a vector function with the
149 kinetic rates of hydrolysis and substrate (sugars, amino acids, hydrogen) utilization.
150 Hydrolysis rates are described by first-order kinetics. Substrate utilization rates are
151 described by the Monod kinetics. \mathbf{S} is the stoichiometry matrix containing the yield
152 factors ($Y_{i,j}$) of each metabolite (i) for each reaction (j), $\mathbf{g}(\cdot)$ is a vector function with
153 the equations representing transport phenomena (*i.e.*, input/output fluxes, liquid–gas
154 transfer), and \mathbf{p} is the vector of the model parameters. The model is detailed in
155 Blondiaux et al. (2025). The implementation of the model is available in the R
156 software (Blondiaux, 2024). Few modifications were done in the original model for
157 constructing the OED approach. The modified model was implemented in Matlab
158 R2019b. In the scripts, state variables in capitals refer to quantities in mass or molar
159 units. For example $S_{ac} = s_{ac} \cdot V_1$. Table 1 shows the model parameters. In this work,
160 we focused on the parameters associated to the effect of *A. taxiformis* on the rumen
161 fermentation and methane production. *A. taxiformis* contains the anti-methanogenic
162 compound bromoform which inhibits directly the growth rate of methanogens. The
163 dynamics of bromoform concentration s_{br} follows

$$164 \quad \frac{ds_{br}}{dt} = F_{br,in} - k_{br} \cdot s_{br} - F_{br,out} \quad (3)$$

165 Where $F_{br,in} = \frac{w_{br} \cdot DMI}{V_1}$ is the input flux of bromoform concentration (g/(L h)) with w_{br}
166 the fraction of bromoform in the diet of the animal. We assumed a bromoform content
167 in the macroalgae of 0.684% in the DM (Chagas et al., 2019), therefore $w_{br} =$
168 0.00684. w_{AT} , where w_{AT} is the fraction of *A. taxiformis* in the feed (in DM). The

169 parameter k_{br} is the kinetic rate constant of bromoform utilization (h^{-1}) and $F_{br,out} =$
 170 $D \cdot s_{br}$ is the output flux of bromoform concentration (g/(L h)), with D the dilution rate
 171 constant set to $D = 0.035 h^{-1}$ (Bayat et al., 2011) to represent conditions close to the
 172 *in vivo* situation. The direct inhibition of bromoform is integrated in the kinetic rate of
 173 hydrogen utilization (ρ_{H_2}) by the methanogens:

$$174 \quad \rho_{H_2} = I_{br} \cdot I_{IN} \cdot k_{m,H_2} \frac{s_{H_2}}{K_{s,H_2} + s_{H_2}} x_{H_2} \quad (4)$$

175 where s_{H_2} (mol/L) is the hydrogen concentration in liquid phase, x_{H_2} (mol/L) is the
 176 concentration of hydrogen-utilizing microbes (methanogens), k_{m,H_2} (mol/(mol h)) is
 177 the maximum specific utilization rate constant of hydrogen, K_{s,H_2} (mol/L) is the Monod
 178 affinity constant of hydrogen utilization, and I_{IN} is a nitrogen limitation factor. The
 179 factor I_{br} represents the inhibition caused by the bromoform on the growth of
 180 methanogens growth and follows the non-competitive inhibition equation

$$181 \quad I_{br} = \frac{k_{I,br}}{k_{I,br} + s_{br}} \quad (5)$$

182 With $k_{I,br}$ the bromoform inhibition constant. It should be noted that in the previous
 183 model versions (Blondiaux et al., 2025; Muñoz-Tamayo et al., 2021), I_{br} was
 184 represented by a sigmoid function. In the present work, we modified the
 185 representation to the rational Eq. (5) to facilitate the identifiability analysis which can
 186 become difficult when using exponential functions (see Muñoz-Tamayo and
 187 Tedeschi, 2023 for discussion on parameter identifiability of exponential functions).
 188 An indirect effect of bromoform on the fermentation takes place due to H_2
 189 accumulation under CH_4 inhibition conditions. The carbon flux allocation towards the
 190 production of volatile fatty acids (VFA) from sugars is driven by the partial pressure of
 191 hydrogen (p_{H_2}) which increases when methane production is inhibited. Sugars
 192 utilizers convert glucose into VFA following the following macroscopic reactions:

196 The flux allocation is determined by the model parameters $\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3$ that represent
197 the molar fraction of glucose utilized to produce acetate, propionate and butyrate,
198 respectively. They follow $\lambda_1 + \lambda_2 + \lambda_3 = 1$. The allocation parameters are
199 represented by the following linear equations

200 $\lambda_1 = p_1 - p_2 \cdot p_{H_2}$ (6)

201 $\lambda_2 = p_3 + p_4 \cdot p_{H_2}$ (7)

202

203 **Parameter identifiability**

204 We focused on the five key model parameters described above representing the
205 effect of *A. taxiformis* on the rumen fermentation and methane production:

206 $k_{I,br}, p_1, p_2, p_3, p_4$. Firstly, we tested their structural identifiability, that is the theoretical
207 ability to recover uniquely their values from measurements given by an experimental
208 setup. The structural identifiability is relevant for the construction of models whose
209 purpose is to predict system behaviour (Muñoz-Tamayo et al., 2018). The interested
210 reader on parameter identifiability is referred to Muñoz-Tamayo and Tedeschi (2023)
211 which provides information on available software tools for identifiability analysis with
212 examples in animal science. We used the software toolbox GenSSI 2.0 (Ligon et al.,
213 2018) to assess the structural identifiability of the five model parameters. GenSSI
214 couples the generating series approach with identifiability tableaux.

215 We assumed that the available measurements were the concentrations of VFA
216 (s_{ac}, s_{bu}, s_{pr}), gas concentrations ($s_{g,CO_2}, s_{g,H_2}, s_{g,CH_4}$) and the concentration of
217 bromoform (s_{br}).

218 ***Optimal Experiment Design for parameter identification***

219 OED aims at obtaining the maximum information to be collected in an experiment on
220 the basis of the optimization of a suitable criterion (Walter and Pronzato, 1990). In
221 our case, the goal of the OED is to provide the conditions of an experiment whose
222 data will be used to obtain accurate parameter estimates of a model representing our
223 system under study. By this, we follow the upstream approach advocated in Muñoz-
224 Tamayo and Tedeschi (2023) to provide high informative data for the construction of
225 robust models. It should be noted that while structural identifiability addresses a
226 qualitative analysis, the OED follows a quantitative approach aiming at improving the
227 practical identifiability of the parameter estimates. That is, to improve their accuracy
228 or reduce their uncertainty. The interested reader on parameter identifiability is
229 referred to Lam et al., (2022) and Wieland et al., (2021). For the OED problem, we
230 used the D-optimality criterion which maximizes the determinant of the Fisher
231 Information Matrix (FIM):

$$232 \min_{\boldsymbol{\varphi}} -\det(\text{FIM}(\mathbf{p}, \boldsymbol{\varphi})) \quad (8)$$

233 Where \mathbf{p} is the parameter vector and $\boldsymbol{\varphi}$ is the design vector that defines the
234 experimental set up. Maximizing the determinant of the FIM is equivalent to minimize
235 the volume of the confidence intervals. We followed the local design approach where
236 the OED is set using the vector of nominal values \mathbf{p}_0 for the parameters ($\mathbf{p} = \mathbf{p}_0$).

237 The FIM is calculated at \mathbf{p}_0 as follows

$$238 \quad \text{FIM}(\mathbf{p}_0, \boldsymbol{\varphi}) = \sum_{i=1}^{n_t} \left[\frac{\partial \mathbf{y}_m}{\partial \mathbf{p}} \right]_{(t_i, \mathbf{p}_0)}^T \boldsymbol{\Sigma}^{-1} \left[\frac{\partial \mathbf{y}_m}{\partial \mathbf{p}} \right]_{(t_i, \mathbf{p}_0)} \quad (9)$$

239 Where n_t is the number of sampling (observation) times and $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}$ is the covariance
 240 matrix of the observed variables. We assumed that the standard deviations of the
 241 observed variables were the same and equal to 5×10^{-4} . The matrix $\frac{\partial \mathbf{y}_m}{\partial \mathbf{p}}$ contains the
 242 first-order sensitivities of the observed variables \mathbf{y}_m with respect to the parameters \mathbf{p} .
 243 The sensitivity equations were obtained by symbolic manipulation in Matlab using the
 244 IDEAS toolbox (Muñoz-Tamayo et al., 2009) which is available at
 245 <http://genome.jouy.inra.fr/logiciels/IDEAS>. The calculation of the sensitivities for $n_p =$
 246 5 parameters results from the resolution of an extended model with $19 + 19 \times n_p =$
 247 114 state variables. The scripts with the extended model and the auxiliary functions
 248 were generated by IDEAS.
 249 We defined the decision vector of the experimental setup as the bromoform content
 250 in the feed as DM, and five sampling times for a run of 24 h: $\boldsymbol{\varphi} = [w_{br}, t_1, t_2, \dots, t_5]$. We
 251 set a minimal difference of 30 min between two sampling times to place our
 252 theoretical exercise in a practical experimental implementation. Accordingly the k th
 253 sampling time was set as $t_k = t_{k-1} + \Delta_k + 0.5$. The parameters Δ_k are to be
 254 estimated in the optimization.
 255 The initial conditions at t_0 were assumed to be known. The maximization of the
 256 determinant of the FIM (Eq. 8) was done using firstly the Matlab function `fminsearch`
 257 (Nelder-Mead Simplex Method). Then, we used the resulting estimates as initial
 258 guess for a global optimization using the MEIGO Matlab software (Egea et al.,
 259 2014). We used the metaheuristic enhanced scatter search method (Egea et al.,
 260 2010) implemented in MEIGO.

261 **Results and discussion**

262 The assessment of structural identifiability with GenSSI 2.0 (Ligon et al., 2018) led to
263 the conclusion that the five model parameters are structurally globally identifiable
264 under the experimental setup. The computational time for the identifiability testing
265 was of 1.9s on a laptop with a 2.40 GHz CPU. Table 2 shows the design vector
266 obtained after the maximization of the determinant of the FIM for each feed
267 distribution pattern. We observed that the optimal solutions are specific to each
268 pattern. If we analyse this outcome in the context of an animal trial in which the
269 animals exhibit different feeding patterns, we can infer that there will be an optimal
270 sampling protocol for each animal. However, for practical reasons, it would be
271 preferable to have a single sampling protocol that could provide accurate
272 measurements for all animals. Such a sampling protocol could be estimated in
273 advance by applying the OED approach to an extended mathematical model that
274 takes into account *in vivo* conditions and incorporates the individual characterisation
275 of animal feeding behaviour.

276 Figure 4 shows the theoretical response of the model under the OED conditions for
277 the distribution with $n_r = 2$, $\omega_1 = 0.7$; $\omega_2 = 0.3$. Table 3 shows the ratio of the
278 standard deviations (s. d.) of the parameters by the OED compared to a design with a
279 classical equidistant sampling with *A. taxiformis* content of 0.5% DM ($w_{br} = 0.0034$)
280 for the four feed distribution patterns. We observed that the gain in accuracy of the
281 OED protocol with respect to the equidistant protocol depends on the dynamic
282 pattern of feed intake. The highest gain was obtained for the feed intake with $n_r = 2$,
283 $\omega_1 = 0.7$, $\omega_2 = 0.3$. The standard deviations (s.d.) of the parameters by the OED
284 protocol were in average 57% of the s.d. of the equidistant sampling protocol. The
285 lowest gain was obtained for the feed intake with scenario $n_r = 4$, $\omega_j = 0.25$. Here, the
286 s.d. of the OED protocol were in average 92% of the s.d. of the equidistant sampling

287 protocol. Table 3 also shows that determinant of the FIM for each feeding pattern.
288 The OED protocol for the feeding pattern with $n_r = 1$ has the highest determinant,
289 and thus it provides the smallest confidence intervals for the estimates. The
290 determinant of the FIM of the OED protocol for the feeding pattern with $n_r = 2$, $\omega_1 =$
291 0.7 , $\omega_2 = 0.3$ is 13 higher to that from the equidistant sampling. These results
292 demonstrate the potential of the OED approach for obtaining accurate parameter
293 estimates, and highlight the importance of selecting an optimal supply of feed
294 additives.

295 The research on structural identifiability is considered to have reached a high degree
296 of maturity (Wieland et al., 2021) supported by the development of a variety of
297 software toolboxes for structural identifiability analysis (Barreiro and Villaverde,
298 2023). On the other hand, practical identifiability analysis requires further
299 developments at the conceptual and technical level (Heinrich et al., 2025a; Wieland
300 et al., 2021). In our work, we used an approach based on the FIM to address the
301 practical identifiability problem because its simplicity of implementation by means of
302 symbolic manipulation via the IDEA toolbox (Muñoz-Tamayo et al., 2009). Here, we
303 focused on a few number of parameters, but the approach can be extended to a
304 larger set of parameters. Considering a large number of parameters however can
305 make difficult the computation of the FIM. One alternative strategy is to partition the
306 full OED problems into smaller sub-problems targeting a couple of parameters
307 (Muñoz-Tamayo, 2014). It must be kept in mind, however, that the use of the
308 approximation of the confidence intervals of the parameters using the FIM is only
309 valid asymptotically under the following conditions (Walter and Pronzato, 1997): *the*
310 *number of data points is large, the nonlinearity of the model with respect to its*
311 *parameters is mild and the measurement errors are independently distributed and*

312 *have small magnitudes*. When these conditions are far from being satisfied, the use
313 of the FIM must be considered with caution. Alternatively, the profile likelihood
314 method (Raue et al., 2009) offers an accurate approach for the assessment of
315 practical identifiability that circumvents the shortcomings of the FIM approach.
316 However, its implementation is computationally expensive (Heinrich et al., 2025b;
317 Villaverde et al., 2022). It would be useful to implement further the profile likelihood
318 approach to our case study and compare it with the results provided by the FIM
319 approach. An example of application of the profile likelihood approach in animal
320 science is presented by Vargas-Villamil et al. (2020) for a sheep nutrition model.
321 To sum up, we showed that the consideration of parameter identifiability within an
322 upstream approach (Muñoz-Tamayo and Tedeschi, 2023) provides a useful resource
323 to improve the identifiability of model parameters and build robust models with
324 capabilities for the prediction of the impact of AMFA on rumen fermentation and
325 methane production. Firstly, by the structural identifiability analysis, we guaranteed
326 that the parameter optimization problem has a unique solution. Secondly, by the
327 design of an optimal experimental scheme, we provided conditions for producing
328 data with high informative content for obtaining accurate parameter estimates. Such
329 an approach allows to get the most out of experimental data and has the potential of
330 minimizing costs of an experimental setup (Muñoz-Tamayo et al., 2018). In the broad
331 context of measuring methane, the OED approach developed here aligns with
332 studies aiming at identifying the best optimal sampling times in devices such as the
333 GreenFeed to obtain accurate measurements (e.g., Van Lingen et al., 2023). The
334 OED approach could also be useful to determine optimal supply of single AMFA and
335 winning combination of additives allowing to address potential drawbacks of impaired
336 synchronization when using combination of additives (Muñoz et al., 2024). To exploit

337 the potential of parameter identifiability and OED, a strong synergy between
338 experimentalist and modellers is required.

339 The next step of this work is to extend the approach to an ongoing modelling project
340 aiming at representing the synergetic effect of combining *A. taxiformis* with the
341 hydrogen acceptor phloroglucinol under *in vitro* conditions (Roger et al., 2025). This
342 strategy aims at reducing methane while improving rumen fermentation. A further
343 application of the OED approach to *in vivo* conditions would be instrumental to
344 improve the connection between *in vitro* and *in vivo* results and better assess the
345 impact of AMFA on the animal. By combining modelling and dedicated experiments,
346 we expect to enhance our understanding on the rumen microbial ecosystem and
347 provide tools to inform the design of strategies for sustainable ruminant production.
348 This approach aligns with the 3Rs (Replacement, Reduction, and Refinement)
349 principle in setting optimal conditions for refining experiments and building *in silico*
350 models that can reduce, in the future, the use of animal experiments for evaluating
351 methane mitigation strategies.

352

353 **Ethics approval**

354 Not applicable.

355 **Data and model availability statement**

356 The scripts of the OED implementation and identifiability testing are available at
357 Muñoz-Tamayo (2026) and in the link:
358 https://github.com/rafaelmunoztamayo/OED_rumen.

359 **Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing**
360 **process**

361 We used the software DeepL to correct the English.

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365 **Declaration of interest**

366 None.

367 **Acknowledgements**

368 We thank Paul Blondiaux and Tristan Senga Kiessé (INRAE, France) for helpful
369 discussions on sensitivity analysis applied to our rumen fermentation model.

370 **Financial support statement**

371 Rafael Muñoz-Tamayo acknowledges funding from the ANR project H2Rumen (ANR-
372 24-CE20-7802).

373 **CRedit Author contributions**

374 Rafael Muñoz-Tamayo: Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Investigation,
375 Methodology, Software, Writing – original draft.

376 Maguy Eugène: Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – review & editing.

377 **References**

378 Arndt, C., Hristov, A.N., Price, W.J., McClelland, S.C., Pelaez, A.M., Cueva, S.F., Oh, J.,
379 Dijkstra, J., Bannink, A., Bayat, A.R., 2022. Full Adoption of the Most Effective
380 Strategies to Mitigate Methane Emissions by Ruminants Can Help Meet the 1.5 °C
381 Target by 2030 but Not 2050. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of*
382 *the United States of America* 119. doi:10.1073/PNAS.2111294119

383 Barreiro, R.X., Villaverde, A.F., 2023. Benchmarking tools for a priori identifiability analysis.
384 *Bioinformatics* 39, btad065. doi:10.1093/bioinformatics/btad065

385 Bayat, A.R., Rinne, M., Kuoppala, K., Ahvenjärvi, S., Huhtanen, P., 2011. Ruminant large and
386 small particle kinetics in dairy cows fed primary growth and regrowth grass silages
387 harvested at two stages of growth. *Animal Feed Science and Technology* 165, 51–60.
388 doi:10.1016/J.ANIFEEDSCI.2011.02.018

389 Belanche, A., Bannink, A., Dijkstra, J., Durmic, Z., Garcia, F., Santos, F.G., Huws, S.,
390 Jeyanathan, J., Lund, P., Mackie, R.I., McAllister, T.A., Morgavi, D.P., Muetzel, S.,
391 Pitta, D.W., Yáñez-Ruiz, D.R., Ungerfeld, E.M., 2025. Feed additives for methane
392 mitigation: A guideline to uncover the mode of action of antimethanogenic feed
393 additives for ruminants. *Journal of Dairy Science* 108, 375–394.
394 doi:10.3168/JDS.2024-25046

395 Belanche, A., Newbold, C.J., Lin, W., Rees Stevens, P., Kingston-Smith, A.H., 2017. A
396 systems biology approach reveals differences in the dynamics of colonization and
397 degradation of grass vs. hay by rumen microbes with minor effects of vitamin E
398 supplementation. *Frontiers in Microbiology* 8. doi:10.3389/fmicb.2017.01456

399 Blondiaux, P., 2024. Implementation of a dynamic sensitivity analysis of a mathematical
400 model describing the effect of the macroalgae *Asparagopsis taxiformis* on rumen
401 fermentation and methane production under in vitro continuous conditions.
402 doi:10.5281/ZENODO.12167243

403 Blondiaux, P., Kiessé, T.S., Eugène, M., Muñoz-Tamayo, R., 2025. Dynamic sensitivity
404 analysis of a mathematical model describing the effect of the macroalgae
405 *Asparagopsis taxiformis* on rumen fermentation and methane production under in

406 vitro continuous conditions. Peer Community Journal 5, e126.
407 doi:10.24072/pcjournal.644

408 Chagas, J.C., Ramin, M., Krizsan, S.J., 2019. In vitro evaluation of different dietary methane
409 mitigation strategies. Animals 9, 1120. doi:10.3390/ani9121120

410 Dijkstra J, Bannink A, Congio GFS, Ellis JL, Eugène M, Garcia F, Niu M, Vibart RE, Yáñez-
411 Ruiz DR, Kebreab E (2025) Feed additives for methane mitigation: Modeling the
412 impact of feed additives on enteric methane emission of ruminants—Approaches and
413 recommendations. Journal of Dairy Science, 108, 356–374.
414 <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2024-25049>

415 Egea, J.A., Henriques, D., Cokelaer, T., Villaverde, A.F., MacNamara, A., Danciu, D.P.,
416 Banga, J.R., Saez-Rodriguez, J., 2014. MEIGO: An open-source software suite
417 based on metaheuristics for global optimization in systems biology and
418 bioinformatics. BMC Bioinformatics 15, 136. doi:10.1186/1471-2105-15-136

419 Egea, J.A., Martí, R., Banga, J.R., 2010. An evolutionary method for complex-process
420 optimization. Computers and Operations Research 37, 315–324.
421 doi:10.1016/j.cor.2009.05.003

422 Heinrich, M., Arutjunjan, R., Timmer, J., 2025a. On the different flavours of practical
423 identifiability. Current Opinion in Systems Biology 42, 100556.
424 doi:10.1016/j.coisb.2025.100556

425 Heinrich, M., Rosenblatt, M., Wieland, F.-G., Stigter, H., Timmer, J., 2025b. On structural and
426 practical identifiability: Current status and update of results. Current Opinion in
427 Systems Biology 41, 100546. doi:10.1016/j.coisb.2025.100546

428 Huang, R., Romero, P., Belanche, A., Ungerfeld, E.M., Yanez-Ruiz, D., Morgavi, D.P.,
429 Popova, M., 2023. Evaluating the effect of phenolic compounds as hydrogen
430 acceptors when ruminal methanogenesis is inhibited in vitro – Part 1. Dairy cows.
431 animal 17, 100788. doi:10.1016/J.ANIMAL.2023.100788

432 IPCC, 2022. Global Warming of 1.5°C. IPCC Special Report on Impacts of Global Warming
433 of 1.5°C above Pre-industrial Levels in Context of Strengthening Response to Climate

434 Change, Sustainable Development, and Efforts to Eradicate Poverty. Cambridge
435 University Press. doi:10.1017/9781009157940

436 Kinley, R.D., Martinez-Fernandez, G., Matthews, M.K., de Nys, R., Magnusson, M., Tomkins,
437 N.W., 2020. Mitigating the carbon footprint and improving productivity of ruminant
438 livestock agriculture using a red seaweed. *Journal of Cleaner Production* 259,
439 120836. doi:10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.120836

440 Lam, N.N., Docherty, P.D., Murray, R., 2022. Practical identifiability of parametrised models:
441 A review of benefits and limitations of various approaches. *Mathematics and
442 Computers in Simulation* 199, 202–216. doi:10.1016/J.MATCOM.2022.03.020

443 Ligon, T.S., Fröhlich, F., Chiş, O.T., Banga, J.R., Balsa-Canto, E., Hasenauer, J., 2018.
444 GenSSI 2.0: multi-experiment structural identifiability analysis of SBML models.
445 *Bioinformatics* 34, 1421–1423. doi:10.1093/BIOINFORMATICS/BTX735

446 Machado, L., Magnusson, M., Paul, N.A., Kinley, R., de Nys, R., Tomkins, N., 2016a.
447 Identification of bioactives from the red seaweed *Asparagopsis taxiformis* that
448 promote antimethanogenic activity in vitro. *Journal of Applied Phycology* 28, 3117–
449 3126. doi:10.1007/s10811-016-0830-7

450 Machado, L., Magnusson, M., Paul, N.A., Kinley, R., de Nys, R., Tomkins, N., 2016b.
451 Dose-response effects of *Asparagopsis taxiformis* and *Oedogonium* sp. on in vitro
452 fermentation and methane production. *J. Appl. Phycol.* 28, 1443–1452.
453 doi:10.1007/s10811-015-0639-9

454 Muñoz, C., Muñoz, I.A., Rodríguez, R., Urrutia, N.L., Ungerfeld, E.M., 2024. Effect of
455 combining the methanogenesis inhibitor 3-nitrooxypropanol and cottonseeds on
456 methane emissions, feed intake, and milk production of grazing dairy cows. *animal*
457 18, 101203. doi:10.1016/j.animal.2024.101203

458 Muñoz-Tamayo, R, 2026. Optimal Experiment Design of a rumen model representing the
459 effect of *Asparagopsis taxiformis* on in vitro fermentation.
460 doi:10.5281/ZENODO.19696662

461 Muñoz-Tamayo, R., Chagas, J.C., Ramin, M., Krizsan, S.J., 2021. Modelling the impact of
462 the macroalgae *Asparagopsis taxiformis* on rumen microbial fermentation and
463 methane production. *Peer Community Journal* 1, e7. doi:10.24072/PCJOURNAL.11

464 Muñoz-Tamayo, R., Giger-Reverdin, S., Sauvant, D., 2016. Mechanistic modelling of in vitro
465 fermentation and methane production by rumen microbiota. *Animal Feed Science and*
466 *Technology* 220, 1–21. doi:10.1016/j.anifeedsci.2016.07.005

467 Muñoz-Tamayo, R., Laroche, B., Leclerc, M., Walter, E., 2009. IDEAS: A parameter
468 identification toolbox with symbolic analysis of uncertainty and its application to
469 biological modelling. In *IFAC Proceedings Volumes*. pp. 1271–1276.
470 doi:10.3182/20090706-3-FR-2004.0211

471 Muñoz-Tamayo, R., Martinon, P., Bougaran, G., Mairet, F., Bernard, O., 2014. Getting the
472 most out of it: Optimal experiments for parameter estimation of microalgae growth
473 models. *J. Process Control* 24, 991–1001. doi:10.1016/j.jprocont.2014.04.021

474 Muñoz-Tamayo, R., Nielsen, B.L., Gagaoua, M., Gondret, F., Krause, E.T., Morgavi, D.P.,
475 Olsson, I.A.S., Pastell, M., Taghipoor, M., Tedeschi, L., Veissier, I., Nawroth, C.,
476 2022. Seven steps to enhance open science practices in animal science. *PNAS*
477 *Nexus* 1, pgac106. doi:10.1093/pnasnexus/pgac106

478 Muñoz-Tamayo, R., Puillet, L., Daniel, J.B., Sauvant, D., Martin, O., Taghipoor, M., Blavy, P.,
479 2018. Review: To be or not to be an identifiable model. Is this a relevant question in
480 animal science modelling? *Animal* 12, 701–712. doi:10.1017/S1751731117002774

481 Muñoz-Tamayo, R., Tedeschi, L.O., 2023. ASAS-NANP symposium: Mathematical Modeling
482 in Animal Nutrition: The power of identifiability analysis for dynamic modeling in
483 animal science: a practitioner approach. *Journal of Animal Science* 101, 1–13.
484 doi:10.1093/JAS/SKAD320

485 Pressman EM, Kebreab E (2024) A review of key microbial and nutritional elements for
486 mechanistic modeling of rumen fermentation in cattle under methane-inhibition. *Front.*
487 *Microbiol.*, 15, 1488370. <https://doi.org/10.3389/FMICB.2024.1488370>

488 Raue, A., Kreutz, C., Maiwald, T., Bachmann, J., Schilling, M., Klingmuller, U., Timmer, J.,
489 2009. Structural and practical identifiability analysis of partially observed dynamical
490 models by exploiting the profile likelihood. *Bioinformatics* 25, 1923–1929.
491 doi:10.1093/bioinformatics/btp358

492 Roger, A., Popova, M., Yáñez-Ruiz, D., Muñoz-Tamayo, R., 2025. A conceptual model of the
493 synergetic effect of combining the anti-methanogenic macroalgae *Asparagopsis*
494 *taxiformis* with the hydrogen acceptor phloroglucinol: a strategy for methane
495 mitigation with fermentation co-benefits for ruminants. *Animal - Science proceedings*
496 16, 482–483. doi:10.1016/j.anscip.2025.07.315

497 Romero, P., Ungerfeld, E.M., Popova, M., Morgavi, D.P., Yáñez-Ruiz, D.R., Belanche, A.,
498 2024. Exploring the combination of *Asparagopsis taxiformis* and phloroglucinol to
499 decrease rumen methanogenesis and redirect hydrogen production in goats. *Animal*
500 *Feed Science and Technology* 316, 116060. doi:10.1016/j.anifeedsci.2024.116060

501 Roque, B.M., Venegas, M., Kinley, R.D., De Nys, R., Duarte, T.L., Yang, X., Kebreab, E.,
502 2021. Red seaweed (*Asparagopsis taxiformis*) supplementation reduces enteric
503 methane by over 80 percent in beef steers. *PLoS One* 16, e0247820.
504 doi:10.1371/JOURNAL.PONE.0247820

505 Van Lingen, H.J., Fadel, J.G., Kebreab, E., Bannink, A., Dijkstra, J., Van Gastelen, S., 2023.
506 Smoothing spline assessment of the accuracy of enteric hydrogen and methane
507 production measurements from dairy cattle using various sampling schemes. *Journal*
508 *of Dairy Science* 106, 6834–6848. doi:10.3168/jds.2022-23207

509 van Lingen, H.J., Fadel, J.G., Yáñez-Ruiz, D.R., Kindermann, M., Kebreab, E., 2021.
510 Inhibited methanogenesis in the rumen of cattle: microbial metabolism in response to
511 supplemental 3-nitrooxypropanol and nitrate. *Frontiers in Microbiology* 12, 2026.
512 doi:10.3389/FMICB.2021.705613

513 Vargas-Villamil LM, Tedeschi LO, Medina-Peralta S, Izquierdo-Reyes F, Navarro-Alberto J,
514 González-Garduño R (2020) A multi-inverse approach for a holistic understanding of

515 applied animal science systems. *Animal*, 14, s238–s249.
516 <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1751731120000877>

517 Villaverde, A.F., Raimundez, E., Hasenauer, J., Banga, J.R., 2022. Assessment of Prediction
518 Uncertainty Quantification Methods in Systems Biology. *IEEE/ACM Transactions on*
519 *Computational Biology and Bioinformatics*. doi:10.1109/TCBB.2022.3213914

520 Walter, E., Pronzato, L., 1997. *Identification of Parametric Models from Experimental Data*.
521 Springer, London.

522 Walter, E., Pronzato, L., 1990. Qualitative and quantitative experiment design for
523 phenomenological models—A survey. *Automatica* 26, 195–213. doi:10.1016/0005-
524 1098(90)90116-Y

525 Wieland, F.G., Hauber, A.L., Rosenblatt, M., Tönsing, C., Timmer, J., 2021. On structural
526 and practical identifiability. *Current Opinion in Systems Biology* 25.
527 doi:10.1016/j.coisb.2021.03.005

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541 **Table 1**

542 Model parameters. The parameters used in the Optimal Experiment Design are

543 marked with *.

Mathematical symbol	Definition	Units	Value
$k_{1,br}^*$	Bromoform inhibition constant	g/L	5.07e-05
λ_1	Molar fraction of the sugars utilized to produce acetate	mol/mol	$p_1 - p_2 \cdot p_{H_2}$
λ_2	Molar fraction of the sugars utilized to produce acetate	mol/mol	$p_3 + p_4 \cdot p_{H_2}$
λ_3	Molar fraction of the sugars utilized to produce acetate	mol/mol	$1 - (\lambda_1 + \lambda_2)$
p_1^*	Intercept of λ_1		0.36
p_2^*	Slope of λ_1		0.64
p_3^*	Intercept of λ_2		0.38
p_4^*	Slope of λ_2		0.12
$\sigma_{ac,aa}$	Stoichiometry coefficient of acetate production from amino acids utilization	mol/mol	0.67
$\sigma_{bu,aa}$	Stoichiometry coefficient of butyrate production from amino acids utilization	mol/mol	0.24
$\sigma_{pr,aa}$	Stoichiometry coefficient of propionate production from amino acids utilization	mol/mol	0.062
$\sigma_{H_2,aa}$	Stoichiometry coefficient of hydrogen production from amino acids utilization	mol/mol	0.82
$\sigma_{IC,aa}$	Stoichiometry coefficient of inorganic carbon production from amino acids utilization	mol/mol	0.88
f_{H_2}	Fraction of hydrogen utilized for product formation	mol/mol	$1 - 10 \cdot Y_{H_2}$
f_{su}	Fraction of glucose utilized for product formation	mol/mol	$1 - \frac{5}{6} \cdot Y_{su}$
$f_{ch,x}$	Mass fraction of carbohydrates in the microbial cells	g/g	0.20
$f_{pro,x}$	Mass fraction of proteins in the microbial cells	g/g	0.55
k_{br}	Kinetic rate constant of bromoform utilization	h ⁻¹	0.095

k_d	Death cell rate constant	h^{-1}	8.33e-04
$k_{hyd,ndf}$	Hydrolysis rate constant of cell wall carbohydrates	h^{-1}	0.024
$k_{hyd,nsc}$	Hydrolysis rate constant of non-structural carbohydrates	h^{-1}	0.06
$k_{hyd,pro}$	Hydrolysis rate constant of proteins	h^{-1}	0.09
$k_{m,aa}$	Maximum specific utilization rate constant of amino acids	mol/(mol h)	2.00
k_{m,H_2}	Maximum specific utilization rate constant of hydrogen	mol/(mol h)	16
$k_{m,su}$	Maximum specific utilization rate constant of glucose	mol/(mol h)	1.00
$K_{s,aa}$	Monod constant associated with the utilization of amino acids	mol/L	6.40e-03
K_{s,H_2}	Monod constant associated with the utilization of hydrogen	mol/L	5.84e-06
$K_{s,su}$	Monod constant associated with the utilization of glucose	mol/L	9.00e-03
$K_{s,IN}$	Nitrogen limitation constant	mol/L	2.0e-04
Y_{aa}	Microbial biomass yield factor of amino acids utilizers	mol/mol	0.31
Y_{H_2}	Microbial biomass yield factor of hydrogen utilizers	mol/mol	0.006
Y_{su}	Microbial biomass yield factor of glucose utilizers	mol/mol	0.16
$Y_{ac,su}$	Yield factor of the acetate during utilization of glucose	mol/mol	$f_{su} \cdot (2 \cdot \lambda_1 + \frac{2}{3} \cdot \lambda_2)$
$Y_{bu,su}$	Yield factor of the butyrate during utilization of glucose	mol/mol	$f_{su} \cdot (\lambda_3)$
$Y_{pr,su}$	Yield factor of the propionate during utilization of glucose	mol/mol	$f_{su} \cdot (\frac{4}{3} \cdot \lambda_2)$
$Y_{H_2,su}$	Yield factor of the hydrogen during utilization of glucose	mol/mol	$f_{su} \cdot (4 \cdot \lambda_1 + 2 \cdot \lambda_3)$
$Y_{IN,su}$	Yield factor of the inorganic nitrogen during utilization of glucose	mol/mol	$-Y_{su}$
$Y_{C,su}$	Yield factor of the inorganic carbon during utilization of	mol/mol	$f_{su} \cdot (2 \cdot \lambda_1 + \frac{2}{3} \cdot \lambda_2 + 2 \cdot \lambda_3)$

$Y_{\text{CH}_4, \text{H}_2}$	glucose Yield factor of the methane during utilization of hydrogen	mol/mol	$f_{\text{H}_2} \cdot \left(\frac{1}{4}\right)$
$Y_{\text{IC}, \text{H}_2}$	Yield factor of the inorganic carbon during utilization of hydrogen	mol/mol	$-\left(\left(\frac{1}{4}\right) \cdot f_{\text{H}_2} + \left(\frac{5}{10}\right) \cdot (1 - f_{\text{H}_2})\right)$
$Y_{\text{IN}, \text{H}_2}$	Yield factor of the inorganic nitrogen during utilization of hydrogen	mol/mol	$-Y_{\text{H}_2}$
$Y_{i, \text{aa}}$	Yield factor of the component i during utilization of amino acids	mol/mol	$(1 - Y_{\text{aa}}) \cdot \sigma_{i, \text{aa}}$
$Y_{\text{IN}, \text{aa}}$	Yield factor of the component inorganic nitrogen during utilization of amino acids	mol/mol	$N_{\text{aa}} - Y_{\text{aa}} \cdot N_{\text{mb}}$
$K_{\text{a}, \text{CO}_2}$	Equilibrium constant of bicarbonate		5.13e-07
$K_{\text{a}, \text{NH}_4}$	Equilibrium constant of ammonium		1.44e-09
$K_{\text{a}, \text{VFA}}$	Equilibrium constant of VFA		1.74e-05
K_{w}	Equilibrium coefficient of water		2.75e-14
$k_{\text{L}a}$	Liquid-gas transfer constant	h^{-1}	8.33
$K_{\text{H}, \text{CO}_2}$	Henry's law coefficient of carbon dioxide	M/bar	2.46e-02
$K_{\text{H}, \text{CH}_4}$	Henry's law coefficient of methane	M/bar	1.10e-03
K_{H, H_2}	Henry's law coefficient of hydrogen	M/bar	7.23e-04
P	Pressure	bars	1.01325
T	Temperature	K	312.15
w_{aa}	Molecular weight of average amino acid	g/mol	134
w_{ac}	Molecular weight of acetate	g/mol	60.05
w_{bu}	Molecular weight of butyrate	g/mol	88.10
w_{mb}	Molecular weight of microbial cells	g/mol	113
w_{pr}	Molecular weight of propionate	g/mol	74.1
w_{su}	Molecular weight of glucose	g/mol	180.16
V_{g}	Volume of the gas phase	L	0.06
V_{l}	Volume of the liquid phase	L	0.74

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546 **Table 2**

547 Optimal design vectors obtained after maximization of the determinant of the Fisher
 548 Information Matrix for four feed distribution patterns. The daily dry matter intake
 549 pattern is determined by the number of feed distributions n_r and the fraction ω_j of the
 550 total DM supplied in the distribution j .

$n_r = 1$					
w_{AT} (% DM)	t_1 (h)	t_2 (h)	t_3 (h)	t_4 (h)	t_5 (h)
0.25	9.8	10.7	11.2	23.5	24
$n_r = 2 \omega_j = 0.5$					
w_{AT} (% DM)	t_1 (h)	t_2 (h)	t_3 (h)	t_4 (h)	t_5 (h)
0.51	3	13.5	14.2	21.4	22
$n_r = 2 \omega_1 = 0.7 \omega_2 = 0.3$					
w_{AT} (% DM)	t_1 (h)	t_2 (h)	t_3 (h)	t_4 (h)	t_5 (h)
0.30	8.7	9.2	18	23.4	24
$n_r = 4 \omega_j = 0.25$					
w_{AT} (% DM)	t_1 (h)	t_2 (h)	t_3 (h)	t_4 (h)	t_5 (h)
0.60	8.3	13	13.5	23.5	24

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558 **Table 3**

559 Ratio of the standard deviation (s. d.) of the parameter estimates from the OED to the
 560 s. d. from a design with equidistant sampling (ES) and *A. taxiformis* content of 0.5%
 561 DM for four feed distribution patterns. The daily dry matter intake pattern is
 562 determined by the number of feed distributions n_r in one day and the fraction ω_j of
 563 the total DM supplied in the distribution j .

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		k_1	p_1	p_2	p_3
$n_r = 1$	$100 \frac{\text{s. d. OED}}{\text{s. d. equidistant sampling}}$	75	47	67	54
		$\frac{\det(\text{FIM}) \text{ OED}}{\det(\text{FIM}) \text{ ES}} = \frac{3.5087e + 20}{4.0332e + 19} = 8.70$			
$n_r = 2$	$100 \frac{\text{s. d. OED}}{\text{s. d. equidistant sampling}}$	97	69	69	72
$\omega_j = 0.5$		$\frac{\det(\text{FIM}) \text{ OED}}{\det(\text{FIM}) \text{ ES}} = \frac{2.7881e + 18}{5.6142e + 17} = 5.0$			
$n_r = 2$	$100 \frac{\text{s. d. OED}}{\text{s. d. equidistant sampling}}$	103	37	53	35
$\omega_1 = 0.7$		$\frac{\det(\text{FIM}) \text{ OED}}{\det(\text{FIM}) \text{ ES}} = \frac{1.3714e + 19}{1.0377e + 18} = 13.22$			
$\omega_2 = 0.3$		$\frac{\det(\text{FIM}) \text{ OED}}{\det(\text{FIM}) \text{ ES}} = \frac{1.1883e + 19}{2.7790e + 18} = 4.30$			
$n_r = 4$	$100 \frac{\text{s. d. OED}}{\text{s. d. equidistant sampling}}$	99	110	74	100
$\omega_j = 0.25$		$\frac{\det(\text{FIM}) \text{ OED}}{\det(\text{FIM}) \text{ ES}} = \frac{1.1883e + 19}{2.7790e + 18} = 4.30$			

565

566 **Figure captions**

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569 **Fig. 1.** Daily dry matter intake pattern with two distributions ($n_r = 2$) with the first
570 distribution accounting for 70% of the total DM ($\omega_1 = 0.7$; $\omega_2 = 0.3$).

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573 **Fig. 2.** Representation of the flow transport of the *in vitro* rumen fermentation system.

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 577 **Fig. 3.** Macroscopic representation of the rumen fermentation process and the impact
 578 of *A. taxiformis* on the methanogenesis and on the fermentation from (Muñoz-Tamayo
 579 et al., 2021). Hydrolysis of carbohydrates (fiber and non-fiber) and proteins releases
 580 respectively sugars and amino acids soluble monomers which are utilized by specific
 581 functional microbial groups. Substrate utilization results in product formation (single
 582 arrows) and microbial biomass (double arrows). The bromoform contained in *A.*
 583 *taxiformis* produces a direct inhibition of the growth rate of methanogens that results
 584 in a reduction of methane production and in an accumulation of hydrogen. The symbol
 585 indicates the direct effect of the bromoform on the methanogenesis. Hydrogen
 586 exerts a thermodynamic control on the flux allocation towards volatile fatty acids
 587 production. The symbol indicates the hydrogen control effect on the rumen
 588 fermentation.

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590 **Fig. 4.** Theoretical dynamic response of the model variables under the Optimal
 591 Experiment Design conditions for two feed distributions at 70% and 30% of the total
 592 DM ($n_r = 2$, $\omega_1 = 0.7$; $\omega_2 = 0.3$). The circles • are the optimal sampling times.